

A study on the structural change of business management model under the influence of artificial intelligence

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Abstract

In the face of the era changes brought by artificial intelligence, we have to lay out the layout ahead of time before its technical turning point, so as to create a good market environment for the development of artificial intelligence. Encouraging enterprises to carry out scientific and technological research, the future output value of artificial intelligence will greatly stimulate social and economic transformation and undertake the demand for workload that gradually overflows from human beings. At the same time, the development of artificial intelligence will probably change the economic and social structure. Whether at the national level or at the individual level, we should make a good response in advance and bet on the artificial intelligence industry in advance to get a place in this revolution. The rapid development of artificial intelligence has greatly improved the working and living efficiency of human beings and will promote multi-dimensional integration from the Internet to the Internet of Things. We still have a long way to go in the application of artificial intelligence. This paper makes an analysis from the macro and application perspectives, combining with the related research on artificial intelligence, deeply analyzes the far-reaching impact of artificial intelligence on the economy and society, and puts forward how society, enterprises, and individuals will better respond to the rise of artificial intelligence technology.

Keywords: *Economic and social change; Stratum differentiation; Artificial intelligence social discussion; Application of artificial intelligence; Artificial intelligence risk warning.*

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Introduction

The concept of artificial intelligence (AI) came into being almost gradually during the third industrial revolution (Tredinnick et al., 2017) and has become one of the key topics in recent years. With the development of information technology and the progress of science and technology, artificial intelligence began to appear in human life and began to establish a new order (Melnik et al., 2019). Since the emergence of artificial intelligence, the contribution of artificial intelligence to social development has been obvious to all. Social development has made remarkable achievements, and remarkable achievements have been made in many fields (Wright, 2018). People make use of artificial intelligence and high technology to vigorously promote the development of society and do everything possible to make society move in a harmonious direction (Goralski & Tan, 2020). At the same time, the research results of artificial intelligence also show that, in some aspects, computers are superior to human abilities. Of course, the core problem of artificial intelligence is still to better link human intelligence with machine intelligence and

manage the coordinated development of artificial intelligence and society, which is becoming more prominent (Thiebes et al., 2021).

In our current social life, many of our daily behaviors often interact with artificial intelligence, which greatly facilitates our lives. It can be said that artificial intelligence is no longer the field of future scientists (Dwivedi et al., 2021), but has become an important component of many business models and economic models, and it is also an important direction for the future development of many industry fields (Trajtenberg, 2018).

Artificial intelligence has brought about structural changes in the economy and society, which has aroused the research interest of scholars, and it has gradually become an important research direction in the field of artificial intelligence in recent years. Ilkka (2018) put forward the influence of artificial intelligence on learning and education, providing forward-looking guidance for follow-up research and providing conceptual basis for other research activities to cope with social changes brought by artificial intelligence; Ahuja (2019) put forward the influence of artificial intelligence on the medical field. Based on the advantages of artificial intelligence, combined with the research in the medical field, Ahuja (2019) tried to find the conditions and related requirements for AI to better function in the field of medicine; Petropoulos (2018) proposed the impact of artificial intelligence on employment; Bulchand-Gidumal (2020) put forward the influence of artificial intelligence on the entertainment industry, analyzed the main process of artificial intelligence changing the entertainment industry, and identified the new application of artificial intelligence needed to solve the industry. Because the research on artificial intelligence tends to be in a single field and there is no analysis of the economic and social environment, I will completely analyze and study the structural changes in the economy and society brought by artificial intelligence.

In this paper, the analysis of the impact of artificial intelligence on the economy and society will help people cope with future challenges in advance and begin to adapt to the structural changes of the impact of artificial intelligence on society and individuals. This will explain the impact of artificial intelligence on the systemic economic and social structure change from a macro perspective, that is, the impact of artificial intelligence on the social environment and business model (Lee et al., 2019), including the impact of artificial intelligence on import and export trade, bulk commodity trading, enterprises, employment situation, and international trade. This study will also explain the influence of artificial intelligence on the structural change of systemic economic society from the perspective of application, that is, the influence of artificial intelligence on personal daily life, including home applications, vehicle-mounted artificial intelligence, and industrial artificial intelligence (Strelkova, 2017). Based on the analysis of the two dimensions, it would provide guidance on how we should deal with the impact of artificial intelligence. The relevant significance of the research and the novelty of the research subject are provided, and the relevant conclusions and reflections brought by the impact of artificial intelligence are given.

Based on the two major angles to be involved (macro angle and from the perspective of application), this paper analyzes the impact of artificial intelligence and explores the structural changes of economy and society brought by artificial intelligence. The first angle analyzes the artificial intelligence from the macroscopic angle regarding the impact on the structural change of systemic economy and society. Therefore, we need relevant data, empirical research, and an understanding of the business environment and business behavior under artificial intelligence (Di Vaio et al., 2020). In order to obtain relevant data, we look for research reports and data about artificial intelligence in the past five years and use relevant information and examples to prove it. The second angle is to analyze the impact of artificial intelligence on systemic economic and social changes from the perspective of application and explore the influence of artificial intelligence on human life and daily work. Because the angle is personal, the main purpose is to determine the degree and way that artificial intelligence has changed the daily lives of individuals (Elliott, 2019) and to provide individuals with methods and a basis to adapt to the era of artificial intelligence.

Literature Review

Technological innovation can be traced back to the industrial revolution, and its significant development moment has changed the maximum workload that human beings have achieved. It can be said that the development of technology has driven the progress of living standards and civilized times. With the coming of the third industrial revolution, the emergence of artificial intelligence will have a profound impact on us. Makridakis (2017) said that the related inventions of the artificial intelligence revolution will bring great changes to human society. Even affecting the daily life of the whole society, people who are good at using this technology will gain unique advantages. Let it win in the market competition and gain an advantage.

Artificial Intelligence

In recent years, artificial intelligence has entered a period of vigorous development. With the improvement of various algorithms and the application of the data industry, the development of the artificial intelligence industry has been greatly promoted. Artificial intelligence has significantly improved people’s work efficiency and ability in various fields. What is artificial intelligence? The so-called artificial intelligence is that machines imitate human behavior, which can be roughly divided into the following five categories: first, the ability to collect information, that is, to collect the information seen, heard and touched; The second is the ability to analyze information, that is, the ability to judge things by using collected information and have functional association, and to redefine new problems encountered by using collected information; Third, the ability to transmit information; Fourth, have the ability of self-learning, and gradually learn more useful information and store it through the information collected and delivered by oneself; Fifth is having a certain creative ability. By splicing and combining the collected multi-dimensional information, we can have a new interpretation of this information and play a greater role.

The development of artificial intelligence mainly depends on the development of infrastructure such as mobile internet, big data, and supercomputers. Among them, the application of artificial intelligence to data and the logic and ability of basic calculation are important signs that determine whether artificial intelligence is strong or not.

Table 1. Current development of artificial intelligence

Intelligent+	Retail, intelligent services, autonomous driving, pan-entertainment (Economic high-quality development)	AI, medical care, convenience, intelligent transportation, AI+ education (people having a good life)		smart city AI for few (Modernization of governance capacity)		Synthetic digital content, multi-modal virtual reality (Exploring new models in the future)	
AI New capital construction	Wisdom Zhongtai	Voice technology	Computer vision technology skill	natural language understand	Knowledge map	AR/VP/MP	User login
	Xinsuanli	Cloud data center	New algorithm	Deep learning	New elements	Internet big data	
		Intelligent computer center		Depth map learning		Public services big data	
		Edge calculation		Intensive study			Industry big data
				Small sample learning		Automatic machine learning	
Intelligent base	New connection	Intelligent sensing device	New security	Network security	New system	Laws and regulations	

		Preparation of devices		Terminal security		
		Internet of things		Business security		Ethical norms
		5G		Application safety		
		blockchain		Data security		Standard evaluation
		LBS		Safety management		

Characteristics of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence has the ability to self-learn and self-improve, but at present, most of the products that can achieve complete artificial intelligence remain in the concepts mentioned. It is in the primary stage, lacking a large number of data demonstrations and intelligent testing, and the testing on the application side is particularly weak. However, the development of artificial intelligence in the theoretical section has reached a certain height, such as Google’s AlphaGo, which enables it to calculate and be superior to that of human beings.

Artificial intelligence can collect and distribute data through a variety of channels, sort out cloud data, and collect information from a single project without networking, and in both cases, it has certain growth. It can also collect and calculate output and execute information externally through hardware, so as to achieve the integrated judgment and delivery capability of specific projects. Artificial intelligence has accelerated its development, showing new features such as deep learning, cross-border integration, man-machine collaboration, group intelligence openness, and self-control.

Application Scope of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence has a wide range of applications, including in family, industrial, and military fields. The main application scenarios that speed up human decision-making for data screening and data identification belong to the primary artificial intelligence application, but even the primary artificial intelligence application has greatly reduced people’s working hours and improved people's work efficiency. As shown in Figure 1, the application scope of artificial intelligence has penetrated into all aspects of people's lives and has had a profound impact on people's development.

Figure 1. Application scope of artificial intelligence

Research on Artificial Intelligence

With the continuous development of artificial intelligence, many candidates have conducted profound research on the field of artificial intelligence and predicted its development. Dwivedi et al. (2021) raised the core opinions of some leading experts in the impact and challenges of artificial intelligence in multiple domains, including social, economic, data, organizational, technical, political, and moral challenges. Of course, they also put forward the corresponding areas, mainly from the production, retail, and medical fields, for a brief analysis to explore the possible application scenarios of artificial intelligence in the future.

Similarly, some researchers have unique opinions on future predictions. For example, Katz (2017) emphasized that artificial intelligence will begin to enter human collaborative environments. It is like helping humans accomplish some sophisticated or complicated task. Its role is mainly to assist, not to replace all the people in the whole industry. Stead (2018) also emphasized the role of artificial intelligence as assistance, prediction, and calculation, while human beings played the role of controlling artificial intelligence and then making decisions, and deeply analyzed the future positioning of artificial intelligence.

Bughin et al. (2018) estimated that by 2030, large factories around the world will adopt artificial intelligence technology for assembly lines or other simple and procedural work to replace human beings. This way, it will improve the overall efficiency of the factory and reduce staff expenses. During this period, the technology of artificial intelligence has been developed, its application scope and conditions have increased significantly, and the external manifestations have become various, resulting in the concept of industrial automation. The overall industry has been significantly developed.

Development Status of Artificial Intelligence

Nowadays, the use of artificial intelligence makes events more intelligent and convenient (e.g., speech recognition, customer service, human-computer interaction, recommendation engines, intelligent push). These are all examples of the artificial intelligence around us. The rapid development of artificial intelligence forces enterprises to join in the use of artificial intelligence, making the research and development of artificial intelligence the core decision-making factor, thus creating the economy and profits. Andrew Ng is an internationally renowned scholar, who once founded Google Brain and gave a speech on the MSX project as an adjunct professor at Stanford University. He said, “*Artificial intelligence, like the influence of electricity in the second industrial revolution, has changed most of our lifestyles in contemporary times*” (Lynch, 2017).

Influence of Artificial Intelligence on Systemic Economic and Social Structure Change from Macro Perspective

Consideration of Artificial Intelligence of Governments in Various Countries

As a strategic technology leading the future, artificial intelligence is highly valued by countries all over the world. Every country has formulated its corresponding development strategy in the field of artificial intelligence and occupied the highest point before this information revolution. Artificial intelligence is an important driving force of a new round of economic revolution and industrial revolution leading the future strategic technology, and it is also a new engine of international competition and economic development, which has great political and economic significance for the development of all countries. Who can master the dominance of this new technology in the future, and who will occupy a certain first-mover advantage before the next information revolution and economic transformation? The following arrangements have been made to cope with the new round of artificial intelligence competition:

Table 2. Development considerations of artificial intelligence in various countries

Country	Year	Policy
United States of America	2011	National Robot Development Plan
	2013	The White House Committee on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning was established.
	2016	“Preparing for the Future of Artificial Intelligence” and “National Strategic Plan for Artificial Intelligence Research and Development”
	2017	Artificial Intelligence, Automation and Economy
	2018	National Robot Development Plan 2.0, Artificial Intelligence and National Security, Artificial Intelligence and Future Act
Japan	2018	Hold the "Artificial Intelligence Summit"
	2019	Signed the "American Artificial Intelligence Initiative"
China	2015	“Made in China 2025” and “The State Council's Opinions on Actively Promoting the ‘internet plus’ Action”
	2016	Implementation Plan of “internet plus” Artificial Intelligence for Three Years Patent Action for Innovation and Development of Intelligent Hardware Industry
	2017	Development Plan of New Generation Artificial Intelligence
European Union	2015	“New Robot Raiders” formulates “Artificial Intelligence Industrialization Engineering Table”
	2016	Japan’s Rejuvenation Strategy and the Fifth Basic Plan of Science and Technology
	2017	Artificial Intelligence Technology Raiders, Comprehensive Strategy of Science and Technology Innovation 2017
European Union	2014	European Robot Technology Raiders 2014-2020, Horizon 2020 Strategy-Robot Development Strategic Map
	2016	Draft Recommendations to the EU Committee on Robot Civil Law Rules, EU Robot Civil Legal Rules
	2018	European Union Artificial Intelligence, Ethical Code of Artificial Intelligence

Source: China-Tianji.com

In the future, countries with more advanced artificial intelligence technology will exert certain political pressure on low-level countries. By mastering the technological advantages of new theories such as the Internet, big data, supercomputing, sensor networks, and brain science, countries with insufficient technical reserves will form a long-term data hegemony. Countries with data hegemony will always have a first-mover advantage in social and economic competition. The rise of artificial intelligence may continue to widen the gap in the comprehensive strength of various countries and form a new round of political and economic patterns.

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Enterprises

With the continuous development of globalization and informatization, there are more and more problems encountered by modern enterprises. It can be roughly divided into its own production and operation management, business development, organization, implementation, supervision, and summary. Having a complete set of intelligent office systems can greatly reduce the operating costs of such enterprises.

Efficiency Analysis of Artificial Intelligence in Enterprises

1. Replacement repetitive work

Artificial intelligence’s ability to learn and judge natural language has been able to assist human beings in making effective information screening, and it is tens of thousands of times more than human workload in data analysis and data judgment. Artificial intelligence sharing human repetitive labor can make human intelligence focus on innovation and thinking, improve working efficiency, and increase the labor utilization rate of enterprises.

2. Establish information sharing mechanism

Most enterprises have their own office systems, such as financial and office automation (OA) systems. These office systems have greatly helped enterprises improve their work efficiency, but at the level of information sharing and data co-construction, each system is like an information island, lacking the ability to coordinate the work of various departments. This will lead to more misjudgments in the formulation and implementation of strategies. A leading system or platform can be set up on top of each system, which can solve the problem of information isolation well. The combination of artificial intelligence and cloud computing can go deep into all aspects of enterprise management and timely judge the problems that enterprises may encounter.

3. Using data analysis ability to assist enterprise decision-making

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, the decision-making of traditional enterprises is often difficult to form. Artificial intelligence can be used to track and judge the data of enterprises in a long-term and accurate way. Because artificial intelligence is not mixed with human emotions, it will be more accurate in judging objective facts.

Challenge to Modern Enterprise Management by Manpower

1. Challenges of talent management. The growth of enterprises is as full of strong uncertainty as the growth of human society, and those who rely excessively on artificial intelligence may have serious enterprise lag and management problems. For example, Amazon uses artificial intelligence to judge the behavior of staff to decide whether a person will stay with the company. Lack of certain objective attributes and challenges to traditional management, including excessive emphasis and reliance on artificial intelligence will also make employees with specific talents suitable for the company's development buried in a pile of data, which will make the talent cultivation of enterprises appear homogenized and lack enterprise vitality.

2. Challenges of decision-making management. Because artificial intelligence has a definite tendency to collect data, it will bring mistakes in decision-making to enterprises. Because enterprise management is a multi-dimensional competition, artificial intelligence can only judge and analyze the past. But in an evolving contemporary society, only constant innovation can make enterprises go further. Therefore, artificial intelligence can only be used as a reference tool for our business, and we cannot rely too much on it.

Most enterprises have realized artificial intelligence. The challenges and changes brought by it have led to many positive responses to the arrival of artificial intelligence. The development trend of artificial intelligence is irreversible. As operators and participants in enterprises, only by facing up to the development of artificial intelligence and effectively using its advantages in technology to constantly stabilize their own business models and business ideas can enterprises not fall behind in this era of competition.

3. The influence and change of artificial intelligence on employment forms. The development of artificial intelligence is bound to bring about changes in the employment situation. It is mainly reflected in the following aspects: undertaking the overflowing work demand, creating brand-new jobs, and improving the working efficiency of personnel. At the same time, the development of artificial intelligence is bound to be a change that few people can participate in. The resulting social class differentiation will gradually become obvious. The same is true of every country.

4. The influence of artificial intelligence on international trade. First, the macroeconomic impact of artificial intelligence and related trade effects (Meltzer, 2018). For example, if artificial intelligence can improve productivity, it will promote economic growth and provide new opportunities for

international trade. There are many reasons for the low growth rate of global productivity at present. One reason for low productivity growth is particularly related to understanding the potential connection with artificial intelligence, which is that an economy needs time to absorb and effectively utilize new technologies, especially complex technologies that have an impact on the whole economy, such as artificial intelligence. This includes the time to build a large enough capital stock to produce comprehensive effects, as well as the time to make full use of the supplementary investment (including acquiring skilled talents and business practices) required for artificial intelligence investment.

Influence of Artificial Intelligence on Systemic Economic and Social Structure Change

Home Applied Artificial Intelligence

Home artificial intelligence is usually called a smart home. With the combination of intelligent modules, it can realize the comprehensive utilization of the Internet of Things and the cloud, taking the house as the main body. Edge computing, artificial intelligence, and other technologies make home equipment have terminal management, intelligent control, interconnection, and other functions. They realize the management and construction of the home environment, security, information, and consumption, and combine them with home life to create a good cycle of family living.

According to the data released by the China Household Electrical Appliances Association, in 2019, the accumulated main business income of the whole household electrical appliance industry reached 1.6 trillion yuan, with a total accumulated profit of 133.9 billion yuan. According to Statista data, the smart home market will be worth about 434.5 billion yuan in 2020, and it is expected to exceed 800 billion yuan in 2025, which is in line with the growth rate of 15.8%. The growth rate is amazing.

The application of home-based artificial intelligence is the main driving force for the continuous development of artificial intelligence. Because of its huge consumption base, the data it can master is more accurate, and artificial intelligence has the ability to do deep learning. Using huge amounts of human behavior data can provide customized and personalized services more accurately.

Vehicle-mounted Artificial Intelligence

Vehicle-mounted artificial intelligence is mainly embodied in the fields of human-computer interaction and automatic driving. Human-computer interaction mainly depends on the recognition of human behaviors, such as language and actions, and making corresponding judgments. Among them, there are several functions, such as intelligent navigation, voice broadcasting, behavior monitoring, safety control, and intelligent driving. Intelligent driving is divided into five grades, from L1 to L5, all of which have strict industry standards. Currently, L3 driving experience has been realized. With the continuous breakthrough of the Internet of Things, big data, 5G networks, cloud computing, and other technologies, vehicle-mounted artificial intelligence will fully realize unmanned driving and a more humanized intelligent consumption experience in multiple environments.

Industrial Artificial Intelligence

Industrial intelligence can be classified by the characteristics of ABCDE. These key elements include analytics technology, big data technology, cloud or cyber technology, domain knowledge, and evidence. Analysis (A) is the core of AI. It can only generate value when all the other elements exist. Big data (B) and cloud computing (C) are two essential elements for providing data sources and industrial artificial intelligence platforms. However, professional knowledge (D) and evidence (E) are also two

important factors that are often overlooked. Domain knowledge (D) is a key element in the following matters:

1. Understand the problem and focus on using industrial artificial intelligence to solve it;
2. Understand the system so as to collect accurate and high-quality data;
3. Understand the physical meaning of parameters and how they relate to the physical characteristics of systems or processes;
4. Understand that these parameters vary from machine to machine.

Evidence (E) is also an important element to verify industrial artificial intelligence models and their combination with cumulative learning ability. Only by collecting data on morphological patterns and the evidence associated with them can we improve the AI model to make it more accurate, comprehensive, and keep pace with the times.

Industrial labor is still in the primary stage, and it will take some time for it to be commercialized on a large scale. However, in many fields, the substitution of labor has emerged. Industrial artificial intelligence cannot consider the working environment, working hours, and working mood, and it is a strong substitute for human beings. In the future, human work will rarely be seen in the industrialized human production environment. Industrial artificial intelligence has a high degree of customization and a clear demand. In the future market, without considering political and social factors, there will be a rapid outbreak and occupation of major industries.

How should we deal with the structural changes brought about by artificial intelligence?

Governments of all countries establish a unified management organization.

The development of artificial intelligence is not only at the hardware level but also in more software applications. This will create opportunities for most technical crimes. Because there is no space limitation, countries must manage unified standards for the development direction and application of their technologies. Only co-management and co-governance can avoid large-scale crimes that may be caused by artificial intelligence in the future.

Moreover, with the gradual development of artificial intelligence, the resulting work automation may not reduce the employment rate and unemployment rate of the whole industry in a short period of time, and middle-end jobs are the hardest hit by artificial intelligence technology. In this case, the number of middle-end jobs decreases while the number of low-end and high-end jobs increases, which leads to a widening of the gap, especially when it comes to work pay. Therefore, the government must introduce relevant regulatory policies, such as ensuring the minimum income of residents, increasing tax standards for high-level personnel, and increasing the training of high-tech talents. Under the mediation of this policy, the gap has narrowed. During this period, it is necessary to increase support for low-end jobs, such as financial subsidies, job subsidies, and other welfare benefits.

Create a good market environment.

The development of any new technology is accompanied by controversy, but the technological revolution will not be changed because of the obstruction of a certain regional country or government. All countries that hinder technological development will be in a backward position. Therefore, only by setting a suitable development path for artificial intelligence at the economic, legal, and humanistic levels in advance can we enjoy this technological dividend.

Layout artificial intelligence industry in advance.

Before the fourth industrial revolution, it must have been the information revolution that was the main change. During this period, the demand for relevant information talents rose sharply, and other jobs decreased correspondingly. This must be what will happen in the future. It is believed that with the gradual development of information technology, the demand for artificial intelligence professionals will definitely increase, which is the inevitable process of the development of artificial intelligence. In this case, more people will receive education, and until they are qualified for jobs, except for some existing jobs, the employment opportunity center will be transferred to social work, interpersonal work, and jobs that require creativity. Moreover, no matter at the national or enterprise level, there should be no resistance in the face of market competition brought by manpower. Facing the new technology, we should try to make use of its advanced nature. At the same time, we should be alert to the potential risks brought by the application of artificial intelligence.

Table 3. Demand for new professional talents in the next five years

New career	Quantity (person)
Artificial intelligence related talents	Break through 10 million
Internet of Things installation debugger	5 million
Practitioners of digital managers	Over 2 million
Electronic sportsman	Nearly 2 million
Agricultural manager	1.5 million
Cloud computing engineers and technicians	Nearly 1.5 million
E-sports operator	Nearly 1.5 million
Industrial robot system operator	About 150,000 yuan
Information model technician	Nearly 1.3 million
Operator of industrial robot system	Nearly 1.25 million
Drone	Nearly 1 million
Amount to	Over 28.3 million yuan

Source: New Career Online Learning Platform Development Report

Novelty of the Study

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an emerging industry in China and even around the world, with a relatively short development time. People's attention to AI research has been continuously increasing, and the discussion on AI from all levels of society is mixed. As a major participant in the industrial information revolution, artificial intelligence is bound to be one of the development trends with the development of the Internet and the widespread use of related technologies such as big data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things. In this context, the development prospects of artificial intelligence-related fields are extremely broad, and the application scope and application scenarios of artificial intelligence have increased significantly, but this attention is far from enough. The scope and content of artificial intelligence are wide; from industrial intelligence to household intelligence, from production intelligence to life intelligence, every aspect has a role for artificial intelligence. Research on artificial intelligence is usually limited to a certain industry, a field, or an application scenario; for example, the impact of artificial intelligence on education, on the medical field, and on employment, as mentioned before. It can be found that the macro effects brought by artificial intelligence are rarely discussed, and only a small amount of space is used to describe them in the article. It can be said that artificial intelligence drives the transformation and reform of the economy and society and meets the needs of human work. Therefore, this article attempts to analyze the application of artificial intelligence from a macroscopic angle, combining the social from all walks of life-related applications in the field of artificial intelligence and its influence. In depth analysis, the profound influence of artificial intelligence can bring economic and social benefits to better cope with artificial intelligence with social changes.

Conclusion

The development of artificial intelligence is the inevitable outcome of the progress of the times. Any country or individual that violates the laws of economic and social development will be in a backward position in the competition of the times. However, the development of artificial intelligence must be nonlinear, and the practice of many applications will surely lead to a rapid technological breakthrough in a certain period of time. By then, countries or individuals with powerful artificial intelligence will usher in a new round of competition.

Compared with the industrial revolution, the electrical revolution, and the information revolution, the artificial intelligence revolution has its own unique development path. It can only happen in countries where the previous three revolutions have been completed, and the reasons are not complicated. The development of artificial intelligence needs the construction of these infrastructures. Only countries with complete technology spillovers and resource spillovers can have powerful artificial intelligence applications. Relatively speaking, the development of artificial intelligence relies on algorithmic logic. It will be the only opportunity for weak countries to cultivate talents in basic disciplines before a fixed pattern is formed.

Compared with the development of other technologies, the social problems brought by artificial intelligence will be more prominent. The existing technologies, laws, values, and social risks must be deployed in advance. Otherwise, it will seriously limit the application and development of artificial intelligence.

With the continuous integration of artificial intelligence and big data applications, countries and enterprises with data hegemony are bound to occupy a favorable position in the competition. At the same time, the development of artificial intelligence will never gradually penetrate into weak territory like other technologies, but will have an obvious Matthew effect, and the strong will be strong. In the application field of artificial intelligence, there will be a scene of multiple application vendors going hand in hand. Compared with the basic field, the application field is much less technical, which is determined by the market. There are many brands competing for market share in the manufacturing and sales of similar mobile phones, but the high-end chip market for mobile phones has a highly judged position, which can be manufactured and delivered in batches. This kind of similar scene will probably last for a long time. Every technological change will bring great influence and impact to the economy and society. We can only seize the trend of the times and keep up with the pace of the times. We can do a good job of industrial layout and knowledge layout in advance so as not to be eliminated by the times.

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